

Agro2Circular

D9.3 – Data Management Plan (1st version)

March 2022

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D9.3
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 9 - Project management and coordination activities
Task	T9.3 - Ethical issues management and Data Protection issues
Lead beneficiary	22 (UVEG)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	All partners
Due date of deliverable	31 March 2022
Actual submission date	31 March 2022

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1		First draft of document
v0.2		Revised version based on the comments of Fuensanta Monzó) - CETEC
v1.0		First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v1.1		First draft based upon first final version
v2.0		Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	28/03/2022	Fuensanta Monzó-Project coordinator
V0.2	30/03/2022	WP leader with corrections made by the project coordinator

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Alfonso Gallego	31/03/2022
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó	31/03/2022

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838

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1 List of abbreviations

APC	Article Publishing Charges
DAC	Data Access Committee
DIS	Data Integration System
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EG	Ethylene Glycol
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
FNC	File Naming Convention
F&V	Fruits & Vegetables
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
PE/PET	Polyethylene/Polyethylene Terephthalate
RA	Research Action
TPA	Terephthalic Acid
WP	Work Package

2 Executive summary

This is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the Agro2Circular (A2C) project, prepared for the 6-month point in the project. The DMP describes the data management lifecycle, indicating how research data collected, processed or generated by the A2C project will be handled during and after the completion of the study. Thus, this deliverable aims to inform A2C partners about the main guidelines and good practices that will be applied to the data processed and generated in the project. This DMP defines the methodologies and standards that will be applied in A2C to make the data FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

The DMP has been drafted following the guidelines on FAIR data management in Horizon 2020 and the general template annexed to the document¹.

The DMP is intended to be a living document in which information will be available at a more detailed and specific level through regular updating as the project implementation progresses and when significant changes or milestones occur. The final version of the DMP will be delivered at month 34.

¹ European Commission (2016). *Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*. Available at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

3 Data summary

3.1 A2C project

Agro2Circular (A2C) is a 36-months EU-funded project aiming at the implementation of a territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of most relevant residues in the agrifood sector (Fruits & Vegetables and multilayers) into high added value products, powered by a digital tool and constructed upon a systemic approach with high replicable/scalable potential. A2C systemic solution is based in following strategies:

1. Innovative green hybrid extraction, purification and stabilisation routes to obtain bioactives from F&V wastes.
2. First recycling value chain for post-industrial multilayer films by combining innovative sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination and mechanical recycling.
3. Digital platform for the agrifood sector, traceability in real time and decision support tool for optimal valorisation routes.
4. A2.C multidimensional model and tools fostering the territorial development of circular economy and enabling its replication/scalability, constructed through public engagement and co-creation processes.

A2C has the following objectives:

Objective 1: Demonstrating the first value chain for the upcycling of most representative agrifood sector wastes. Aims to demonstrate the technical viability of specific routes for the valorisation of agrifood wastes (F&V and multilayer plastics).

Objective 2: Providing to the A2C technological solution the circular systemic approach by building a multidimensional model enabling the solution territorial deployment and its replication and scalability.

Objective 3: Maximizing project impacts and facilitating A2C systemic solution replication & scalability.

A2C has 41 international and interdisciplinary partners working on the development of 7 Research Actions (RA), framed in different Work Packages (WP) within the project:

- **RA 1: A2C Specifications, Residues Management and Data Integration System.** The main objectives of this RA are: (i) to define the specifications of the new products along the value chain (ii) to establish strategies for compliance assessment with standards and prepare the recycled materials food contact approval (iii) to define recommendations on water and energy for the new technologies and processes (iv) to perform a management plan for the different residues (v) to characterise the residues (vi) to develop the A2C Data Integration System-DIS.
- **RA 2: A2C technologies for the recycling of the organic agrifood wastes.** RA 2 is aimed at implementing and optimising the technologies for the extraction and recycling of agrifood wastes, including the following specific objectives: i) Establishing the conditioning of agrifood waste ii) Developing the optimal green hybrid extraction routes iii) Purifying and stabilising extracts for their application in new formulations iv) Assessing the quality of extracts and their antioxidant and antimicrobial capacity.
- **RA 3: A2C technologies for the sorting and recycling of multilayer plastics residues.** RA 3 WP3 is aimed to implement the technologies for the sorting and recycling of the multilayers, including these specific objectives: i) To establish plastic waste pre-treatments, including a preliminary decontamination. ii) To develop an optimal sorting. iii) To separate the aluminium from the multilayer materials. iv) To customise enzymes and develop the models for the depolymerisation of PE/PET multilayers to obtain TPA, EG and alkanes. v) To develop PE/PET pre-treatments to enhance the enzymatic attack. vi) To implement a decontamination technology for the plastics from mechanical recycling. vii) To chemically modify the Aluminium to achieve an optimal dispersion in a polyethylene matrix viii) To achieve the optimal processability of the recycled plastic.
- **RA 4. Upcycling of recycled agrifood materials and upscaling.** The main objective of this RA is to demonstrate the application of the extracts in new

formulations at small scale, and to develop at pilot scale the extraction routes and related demonstration of the extraction and purification of the target compounds.

- **RA 5. A2C technologies for the upcycling of the recycled plastics materials.** The main objective consists on obtaining high added value products from the recycled plastic materials.
- **RA 6. Demonstration of the A2C technological solution.** Specific objectives are:
 - i) To integrate physically all the developed technologies at pilot scale up in demonstrators in the south of Spain. ii) To demonstrate all the technologies in a relevant and industrial environment. iii) To manufacture the different A2C prototypes. iv) To set the basis for the future industrial implementation. v) To define the A2C business cases, identifying the specific business models and the financial framework.
- **RA 7. A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability.** This RA is aimed to reach a comprehensive definition of the A2C Systemic solution model and its potential for transferability, by identifying multidimensional impacts but also costs, drivers, challenges and success factors towards the adoption of the A2C.

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of each RA in terms of data processing.

Table 1: Summary of each A2C RA in terms of data processing

	RA1	RA2	RA3	RA4	RA5	RA6	RA7
Type of data to be collected	Waste analysis data Water analysis data Energy analysis data Raw material analysis data Process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams...)	Experimental measurements Process data Analysis of materials and process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams)	Experimental measurements Material analysis and process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams...)	Formulations and validations of cosmetics, food and nutraceuticals enriched with extracts obtained in WP2. (Spreadsheets, surveys) Data of the scale up processes and validation of the extracts obtained (spreadsheets, diagrams, technical datasheets, ...)	Experimental measurements Material analysis and process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams...)	Process data Business and financial data	Socio-demographic data Environmental data Institutional data Economic/market data

<p>Source / origin of data</p>	<p>Generated data at studies</p>	<p>Generated data at up-cycling and up-scale studies</p>	<p>Generated data at studies</p>	<p>Generated data at up-cycling and up-scale studies</p>	<p>Generated data at studies (biodegradability and recyclability data)</p> <p>Generated data at up-cycling and up-scale studies</p>	<p>Existing data</p> <p>Generated data at study sites</p>
<p>Collection methods</p>	<p>Scientific research</p> <p>Interviews</p> <p>Focus Groups</p> <p>Consultation with stakeholders</p> <p>Co-creation sessions</p> <p>Desk research</p>	<p>Scientific research</p> <p>Development of new processes</p> <p>Processes optimization</p>	<p>Scientific research</p> <p>Development of new processes</p>	<p>Scientific research</p> <p>Processes optimization</p>	<p>Scientific research</p> <p>Development of new processes</p> <p>Processes optimization</p>	<p>Surveys</p> <p>Interviews</p> <p>Focus Groups</p> <p>Consultation with stakeholders</p> <p>Co-creation sessions</p> <p>Desk research</p>

<p>Data process</p>	<p>Scientific methods</p>		<p>Scientific method</p>	<p>Statistical analysis of results and evaluation of the optimal conditions/formulations.</p> <p>Scientific method</p>	<p>Quantitative analysis of results obtained from the biotransformation Lab-scale simulation and collection of KPI of each single processing</p> <p>Scientific method</p>		<p>Qualitative methods</p> <p>Quantitative methods</p> <p>LCA-based protocols</p>
<p>Type of data generated</p>	<p>Datasets of individual microdata</p> <p>Textual data (from transcriptions)</p> <p>Secondary documents</p> <p>Web service</p>			<p>Diagrams, Technical datasheets, Formulations</p>	<p>Diagrams, Technical datasheets, Formulations</p>		<p>Datasets of individual microdata</p> <p>Textual data (from transcriptions)</p> <p>Secondary documents</p>

<p>Purpose / Utility of data generated</p>	<p>To evaluate and validate the A2C systemic solution (Data Integration System)</p>	<p>Set the optimal parameters for upscale extraction processes.</p> <p>Set the right proportion of the ingredients/extracts in formulations for cosmetics, foods and nutraceuticals.</p>	<p>Set the optimal parameters for upscaling the microbial and biobased processes of residues upcycling</p>	<p>To evaluate and validate the A2C systemic solution</p>
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3.2 Data generation and collection

Data collection under the A2C project will be as diverse as the topics covered and methodologies used at the seven RAs. An overview of the data to be collected is presented at Table 1. Some data to be collected at the different RAs are not completely specified yet, but main general guidelines on how they will be collected and processed are already defined, which are described below. Additionally, it is important to highlight that A2C consortium claims that data to be collected under the different RAs are adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the research purpose fulfilling the Data Minimization Principle of the GDPR.

Thus, as tasks and methodologies are clarified in the future months, A2C researchers will establish the norms to be used in data collection and data sets to be collected.

Depending on their origin, two main types of data will be used during the A2C lifetime:

- Data purposely generated by project partners under different activities through several means, such as surveys, individual interviews, etc.
- Background data gathered by partners before the start of the project that is relevant in order to perform the project tasks and achieve its objectives.

Personal data will be subject to de-identification and site control, unless written informed consent for very clearly defined research activities is specifically obtained.

Data formats and data types produced under the project depend on how data will be gathered and the software used for their analysis. Clearly, several data types require different file types. As general guidelines, A2C recommends:

- avoiding the use of proprietary software format when possible;
- in case of data files in different formats, converting the data to the most common data format.

4 FAIR Data

4.1 Making data findable

In order to ensure that research data can be used, shared and re-used it is crucial to take care that those data are accessible, understandable and usable. This requires clear data description, annotation, contextual information and documentation explaining how data were created or digitized, what data mean or what their content and structure are.

A2C will encourage establishing strong links between data collected and stored and the associated documentation, following recommendations such as the following:

- Including information within the data or document itself, e.g., in the document properties function of a file or the file header.
- Keeping a database of metadata with links to files.
- Storing a readme.txt file alongside the data which provides basic explanatory details. Txt. Files will be acceptable to explain very simple stuff like how to connect to a database, not the database explanation itself
- Recording relevant context in lab notebooks or associated papers and reports.
- Including link to websites or web pages which explain the context of the research.

4.1.1 Metadata

The use of common data and metadata standards are a key aspect for semantic and technological data operability. Metadata can describe the content, context and provenance of datasets in a standardized and structured manner, typically describing the purpose, origin, temporal characteristics, geographic location, authorship, access conditions and terms of use of a dataset. This provides structured searchable information that helps users to find existing data resources, judge whether a particular dataset is suitable for their research purpose and provides a bibliographic record for citing data. Standard dictionaries of metadata will be used for all data types produced by the data creators. A2C metadata will include different types of metadata:

- Descriptive metadata: describe a resource for the purpose of retrieval and identification. They may contain elements such as title, abstract, author or keywords, etc.
- Structural metadata: relationships between different sets of associated data in the context of databases, such as schema describing associations between tables.
- Administrative metadata: provides the information necessary to help process a resource. An example might be the date of creation or how a resource was created. It may contain several subgroups of administrative information. Among the most common are metadata on rights and metadata for long-term preservation. The latter is one of the primary purposes of repositories.

A2C encourages the use of the Dublin Core metadata schema, characterised by the specification of fifteen "core" elements (properties) to describe resources. These elements have been formally endorsed in the standards ISO 15836², ANSI/NISO Z39.85-2012³ and IETF RFC 5013⁴, and consist of: 1. Contributor, 2. Coverage, 3. Creator, 4. Date, 5. Description, 6. Format, 7. Identifier, 8. Language, 9. Publisher, 10. Relation, 11. Rights, 12. Source, 13. Subject, 14. Title, and 15. Type.

4.1.2 File naming

Structured data storage is essential for a proper and secure storage of data files and records. For any file-based storage this includes clear and unambiguous file naming, the use of proper versioning as well as clear and intuitive folder structure. In this sense, a file naming convention (FNC) helps the project files stay organized by making it easy to identify the file(s) that contain the information from its title and by grouping files that contain similar information close together. A good FNC also helps the consortium members to better understand and navigate through the work performed by other partners.

² ISO (2017). *15836-1:2017 Information and documentation — The Dublin Core metadata element set — Part 1: Core elements*. Available at <https://www.iso.org/standard/71339.html>

³ ANSI/NISO (2013). *Z39.85-2012 The Dublin Core Metadata Element Set*. Available at <http://www.niso.org/publications/ansiniso-z3985-2012-dublin-core-metadata-element-set>

⁴ IETF (2007). *RFC 5013. Dublin Core Metadata*. Available at <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc5013>

A2C will encourage the use of a standard FNC per data type and a clear versioning strategy. Below are some basic rules for the development of A2C FNCs, based on ^{5,6}:

- Find the right balance of components. Too few components create ambiguity; too many limits discovery & understanding.
- Avoid extra-long folder names and complex hierarchical structures but use information-rich filenames instead.
- Abbreviate the content of elements whenever possible and use meaningful abbreviations. File names that contain too many characters can be unwieldy and cause problems in transferring files.
- Use the underscore (_) as element delimiter. Do not use spaces or other characters such as: ! # \$ % &.
- Use the hyphen (-) to delimit words within an element or capitalize the first letter of each word within an element.
- Document your decisions including what components you will use (the "project name" for example), what are the appropriate entries, what acronyms mean, etc.
- Files will be grouped together based on the first few components so start the FNC with the more general components and move to the more specific ones later on. Dates should always be yyyy-mm-dd to organize files chronologically.
- FNC will be shared among all partners of the project in order all individuals who needs to use the FNC are aware of it and knows how to apply it. A file naming convention breaks down if not followed consistently.

4.2 Making data openly accessible

Accessibility means that metadata and data are understandable to humans and machines, and may be retrievable by their identifier via a standardised communication protocol. As stated in Article 29.2 Grant Agreement, each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of

⁵ Purdue University, Libraries and School of Information Studies: <http://guides.lib.purdue.edu/c.php?g=353013&p=2378293>

⁶ Santaguida, V. (2010). *Folder and file naming convention – 10 rules for best practices*. Available at: <http://www.exadox.com/files/pdf/en/Folder-File-Naming-Convention-10Rules-Best-Practice.pdf>

charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, beneficiaries must:

- Deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications, as soon as possible and at the latest on publication.
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher; or within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- Ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications. In this regard, as stated in Article 29.3 Grant Agreement, beneficiaries must also

- Deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible; and other data, including associated metadata.
- Provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and, where possible, provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results, the confidentiality obligations, the security obligations or the obligations to protect personal data.

Article 29.3 also provides that, as an exception, beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data, both for data linked to scientific publications and other data, if the achievement of the main objective of the action is jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data accessible to the public. As a general guideline, A2C will encourage the whole consortium to publish research papers at peer-reviewed open access journals. The following shows some of the data that could be made available in open access via scientific publications, repository hosting or both. Datasets likely to contain personal information will be properly pseudonymised before being made available, respecting the confidentiality and security of the data subjects.

- **Task 1.1 A2C Requirements.** The results of this task will be reported in a public deliverable (A2C requirements).
- **Task 1.2 A2C methodologies.** A pre-dossier EFSA will be reported (EFSA plastics pre-dossier and compliance with agricultural standards D1.5, EFSA agrifood pre-dossier and compliance with food/cosmetic standards D1.6).
- **Task 1.4 A2C residues management and preliminary characterization.** A residues management plan will be generated and it will be reported in three deliverables (D1.2, D1.3 and D1.4)
- **Task 2.2 Extraction of high value-added substances at laboratory scale.** Presentations, posters or technical and scientific papers will be generated.
- **Task 2.3 Purification and stabilisation of extracts.** Presentations, posters or technical and scientific papers will be generated.
- **Sub-Task 3.1.1 Pre-treatments and preliminary decontamination.** Presentation or technical paper will be generated.
- **Task 3.2 Optical sorting of the multilayer materials.** Presentations, posters or technical and scientific papers will be generated, including 2 deliverables (D3.3 and D3.4)
- **Task 3.3 Physical recycling of complex multilayers containing aluminium.** Presentations, posters, or technical and scientific papers could be created describing the separation of aluminium from multilayer structures.

- **Task 3.5 Mechanical recycling of simple multilayer structures and products from physical recycling.** Presentations, posters or technical and scientific papers will be generated.
- **Task 4.1 Formulations of the extracts at small scale.** Presentations and technical information will be generated, including 1 deliverable (D4.1).
- **Task 4.2 Pilot scale up of the optimal extraction routes.** Presentations and technical information will be generated, including 3 deliverables (D4.2, D4.3 & D4.4)
- **Sub-Task 5.1.2, 5.1.3 and 5.1.4: report on PHBV and carotenoids production, recovery and by-product valorization.** Presentations, posters or scientific papers will be generated.
- **Task 5.2 High barrier recycled and recyclable compounds.** Presentations, posters or technical and scientific papers will be generated.
- **Task 5.3 Biodegradable compounds.** Presentations, posters or technical and scientific papers will be generated.
- **Sub task 5.4.1 Compounds transformation.** Presentations, posters or technical and scientific papers will be generated.
- **Sub-task 5.4.2 Validation at small scale.** Presentations, posters or technical papers will be generated.
- **Sub-task 5.4.3 Plastics end life scenarios.** A public deliverable D5.8 Plastic end-life scenarios will be generated.
- **Task 6.1 and 6.2 Integrations and A2C demonstrators.** A deliverable with the integration description and videos from the A2C demonstrators will be generated. Presentations, posters or technical papers will be generated.
- **Task 6.3 Setting the basis for the future industrial implementation.** A public A2C process protocol paper will be generated (D6.4)
- **Task 7.1 Public engagement and community-based schemes.** Public deliverables (D7.1-4) will be generated including the main features of the public engagement strategy and the community-based schemes, its implementation and main results; specific aspects will be included in the policy briefs deliverables (D7.12-13), if relevant. Besides, presentations, posters or scientific papers will be generated including the main results of the public engagement strategy (Sub-task 7.1.1.)

Moreover, the results of the pilot community-based innovation action (Sub-task 7.1.2.) will be reported for publication in a peer-reviewed open access journal.

- **Task 7.4 Social and economic analysis.** The results of this task will be reported for publication in a peer-reviewed open access journal.
- **Task 7.7 Validation of the A2C multidimensional model.** The main results will be included in the associated public deliverable (D7.16) and presentations, posters or scientific papers will be generated.
- **Task 8.8 Standardization activities.** Depending on the A2C standardization strategy (to be developed and implemented), the contribution to the standardization could imply the proposal of revision of existing standards (publicly available) or the development of CEN Workshop agreements (publicly available, free of charge).

4.2.1 Storage

The storage of the data collected and generated under the RAs carried out at A2C will primarily be the responsibility of the joint data controllers. However, A2C will select a data repository where all partners will be encouraged to store research data generated. It is particularly encouraged to store the research data in the Mendeley Data repository (<https://data.mendeley.com/>), as it allows to easily make the data FAIR⁷.

4.2.2 Data access

The documentation describing how to find, get and access data will be described and stored in the selected data repository or software documentation. Thus, no additional documentation will be provided by the A2C project.

For the cases where access to the data needs to be restricted this can be identified at the time the data is submitted to the data repository. Registration to the selected repository will

⁷ Elsevier. *Making your data FAIR with Mendeley Data*. Available at https://www.elsevier.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0013/1012036/ACAD_RES_MDD_INFO_Fair-data-with-Mendeley-Data_WEB.pdf

be necessary as well as access via password in order to obtain A2C data. For restricted data there will be a contact point for requests for data access.

Formats of data to be produced by the A2C consortium at the RAs can be handled by commonly used commercial or open software. Thus, data will be accessible using the same community-standard software.

4.3 Making data interoperable

“Interoperability is the ability to access and process machine-readable data from multiple sources, sometimes automatically, without that data losing meaning or integrity”⁸. In order to achieve this goal, data requires:

- Syntactic interoperability: widespread adoption of standard data formats, and the implementation of application programming interfaces and connectors that allow data from multiple sources to be accessed and integrated;
- Semantic interoperability: data and information must be exchanged across systems without its context and meaning being lost; and
- Search interoperability: it enables a user to conduct queries across two or more collections of data.

Thus, interoperability enables improved data usability and use. For this reason, putting in practice interoperability will be a priority for A2C in order to have the following benefits (among others):

- reducing time, effort and expense spent on data collection;
- eliminating frustration and risks associated with finding inconsistent and incomplete data;
- making available sustainable, disaggregated data for effective decision-making.

⁸ Steele, L., & Orrell, T. (2017). *The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development*. Development Initiatives (p. 5). Available at: https://www.publishwhatyoufund.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/JUDS_Report_Web_061117.pdf

The following is a set of guiding principles for interoperability, based on Open Data Watch⁹, to be applied within the A2C framework:

- Use and re-use existing standards: no new standards should be created in areas they already exist unless absolutely necessary. When new standards are created, they must be compatible with existing standards.
- Do not overlook metadata: metadata is crucial for discoverability, accessibility and fostering trust and understanding of the context in which the data was produced.
- Use common classifications wherever possible: it is important to ensure that to the extent possible, the language used to define and classify that data is the same.
- Publish data in machine-readable formats: it enables a computer to access, identify and filter data in an automated way.
- Ensure that standards are user driven: for data to be usable, it has to be driven by the needs of users themselves. It is crucial to long-term success and impact.

4.3.1 File formats

Table 2 provides an overview of possible formats for data sharing, reuse and preservation to be used in the A2C project.

⁹ Open Data Watch. *What are the principles of joined-up data?* Available at <https://opendatawatch.com/blog/what-are-the-principles-of-joined-up-data/>

Table 2: Formats for data sharing, reuse and preservation

Type of data	Recommended formats	Acceptable formats
Quantitative tabular data with extensive metadata <i>Variable labels, code labels, and defined missing values</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPSS portable format (.por) • Delimited text and command ('setup') file (SPSS, Stata, SAS, etc.) • Structured text or mark-up file of metadata information, e.g. DDI XML file 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proprietary formats of statistical packages: SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb)
Quantitative tabular data with minimal metadata <i>Column headings, variable names</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comma-separated values (.csv) • Tab-delimited file (.tab) • Delimited text with SQL data definition statements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delimited text (.txt) with characters not present in data used as delimiters • Widely-used formats: MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb), dBase (.dbf), OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods)
Qualitative data <i>Textual data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich Text Format (.rtf) • Plain text, ASCII (.txt) • eXtensible Mark-up Language (.xml) text 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypertext Mark-up Language (.html) • Widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx)

	according to an appropriate Document Type Definition (DTD) or schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some software-specific formats: NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
Digital image data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TIFF version 6 uncompressed (.tif) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg) but only if created in this format TIFF (other versions) (.tif, .tiff) Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf) Standard applicable RAW image format (.raw) Photoshop files (.psd)
Digital audio data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Free Lossless Audio CodEC(FLAC) (.flac) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3 (.mp3) if original created in this format Audio Interchange File Format (.aif) Waveform Audio Format (.wav)
Digital video data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPEG-4 (.mp4) OGG video (.ogv, .ogg) Motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVCHD video (.avchd)

Documentation and scripts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich Text Format (.rtf) • PDF/UA, PDF/A or PDF (.pdf) • XHTML or HTML (.xhtml, .htm) • OpenDocument Text (.odt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plain text (.txt) • Widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) • XML marked-up text (.xml) according to an appropriate DTD or schema, e.g. XHTML 1.0
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4.4 Increase data re-use

4.4.1 Long-term use of the data

The main aim is to make the data openly accessible for as long as possible. The decision on the long-term availability of the data collected and processed in the framework of the A2C project will be taken as the data are stored.

After the completion of each task involving data collection, the data will be made openly accessible when the following requirements are met:

- Data collection and processing are completed.
- Data checking - in terms of quality control - is performed.
- The exploitation plan of the consortium partners, both in terms of scientific publications and commercial purposes, is finalised.

The Grant Agreement does not explicitly set any period for the data to be openly accessible. This period will therefore be discussed and agreed by the General Assembly (GA) of the project.

Discussions on licensing and re-use conditions will also be conducted by the project's GA, with the support and/or supervision of the DPO and the Ethics Advisory Board, if necessary.

Finally, data produced during A2C will be re-usable for as long as the information they contain are relevant for further research purposes. Article 28.1 Grant Agreement states that each beneficiary must — up to four years after the end of the project — take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of its results (either directly or indirectly) by:

- using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- creating and providing a service, or
- using them in standardisation activities.

4.4.2 Data quality control

Controlling the quality of data collected under any research is a critical part of the data collection procedures. Data need to be high quality in order the project outcomes and decisions from them can be done on the basis of reliable and valid data. Moreover, data quality is a very important aspect in order to use them for purposes and actions beyond the project ones.

Quality control of data is an integral part of all research and takes place at various stages: during data collection, data entry or digitisation as well as data checking.

During data collection, A2C researchers must ensure that the data recorded reflect the actual facts, responses, observation and actions under study. The following are shown some quality control measures to be taken into consideration during data collection at A2C actions, based on UK Data Service¹⁰:

- Calibration of instruments to check the precision, bias and/or scale of measurement.
- Taking multiple measurements, observations or samples.
- Checking the truth of the record with an expert.
- Using standardised methods and protocols for capturing observations, alongside recording forms with clear instructions.

¹⁰ UK Data Service. *Quality Ensuring quality of data at all stages*. Available at: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/format-your-data/quality/>

- Computer-assisted interview software to: Standardise interviews, verify response consistency, route and customise questions, so that only appropriate questions are asked, confirm responses against previous answers where appropriate and detect inadmissible responses.

When A2C data are entered in a database or spreadsheet (through transcription, digitalization or codification), quality will be ensured by standardised and consistent procedures for data entry with clear instructions. This may include¹¹:

- Setting up validation rules or input masks in data entry software.
- Using data entry screens.
- Using controlled vocabularies, code lists and choice lists to minimise manual data entry.
- Detailed labelling of variable and record names to avoid confusion.
- Designing a purpose-built database structure to organise data and data files.
- Accompanying notes and documentation about the data.

Finally, quality of data can be annualised during data checking; that is when data are edited, cleaned, verified, cross-checked and validated. Some recommendations to be taken into consideration by the A2C consortium during data checking are stated below¹²:

- Double-checking coding of observations or responses and out-of-range values.
- Checking data completeness.
- Adding variable and value labels where appropriate.
- Verifying random samples of the digital data against the original data.
- Double entry of data.
- Statistical analyses, such as frequencies, means, ranges or clustering to detect errors and anomalous values.
- Correcting errors made during transcription.
- Peer review.

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Ibid.

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Costs for making data FAIR

Costs related to open access to research data in the Horizon 2020 programme are eligible costs (article 6.2.D3 - Costs of other goods and services - Grant Agreement) under the conditions defined in the H2020 Grant Agreement.

Resources for long-term preservation of datasets will be ensured by its storage in Mendeley Data.

The costs of making scientific publications open access can vary widely depending on the journal. Converted to euros, the average Article Publishing Charges (APCs) for some of the most relevant publishers are €2,488 for Elsevier journals¹³, €2,250 for Wiley Open Access journals¹⁴, and €1,976 for Springer Nature Open Access journals¹⁵, among others.

These costs will be covered by the A2C budget.

5.2 Responsibilities

Data management responsibilities under A2C project are based on the following figures:

- Joint controllers. In the project there are joint controllers as there are several partners that jointly determine the purposes and means of data processing (art. 26 of the GDPR¹⁶). Controllers shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with the European GDPR.
- Data processors process personal data only on behalf of the controller.

¹³ Elsevier. *Pricing*. <https://www.elsevier.com/about/policies/pricing>

¹⁴ Wiley. *Article Publication Charges (APCs)*. <https://authorservices.wiley.com/author-resources/Journal-Authors/open-access/article-publication-charges.html>

¹⁵ Springer Nature. *Open access journals*. <https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-research/journals-books/journals>

¹⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

- DPO provides expert professional knowledge in data protection law and IT security. The duties of the DPO includes: to inform and advise the controller or the processor and the employees who carry out processing of their obligations pursuant to the GDPR; to monitor compliance with personal data protection regulation; to provide advice where requested as regards the data protection impact assessment and monitor its performance; to cooperate with the supervisory authority; to act as the contact point for the supervisory authority on issues relating to processing, and to consult with regard to any other matter (art. 39.1 GDPR).

Also, a DAC will be established specifically to address issues related to data release to external requestors.

6 Data security

Data security refers to the process of protecting data from unauthorized access and data corruption throughout its lifecycle.

Physical security, network security and security of computer systems and files will be considered and encouraged among the A2C consortium in order to guarantee security of data as well as to prevent unauthorized access, changes to data, disclosure or destruction of data (see Table 3).

Table 3. Security measures

	Description
Physical data security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controlling access to buildings, rooms, cabinets where data, computers, media or hardcopy materials are held. Logging the removal of, and access to, media or hardcopy material in store rooms. Transporting sensitive data only under exceptional circumstances, even for repair purposes; for example, giving a failed hard drive containing sensitive data to a computer manufacturer may cause a breach of security.
Network security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not storing sensitive data such as those containing personal information on servers or computers connected to an external network, particularly servers that host internet services. Firewall protection and security-related upgrades and patches to operating systems to avoid viruses and malicious code.
Security of computer systems and files	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Locking computer systems with a password. Ensuring computer software is up-to-date.

- Protecting servers by power surge protection systems through line-interactive uninterruptible power supply (UPS) systems.
- Implementing password protection and controlled access to data files, for example 'no access', 'read only', 'read and write' or 'administrator-only' permission.
- Controlling access to files, folders or entire hard drives encryption.
- Not sending personal or confidential data via email or other file transfer means without first encrypting them.
- Destroying data in a consistent manner when needed: deleting files and reformatting a hard drive will not prevent the possible recovery of data; consult our guidance on data disposal.
- Imposing non-disclosure agreements for managers or users of confidential data.

Content extracted from UK Data Service¹⁷

Cloud-based storage – specifically Google Drive – will be used by the project consortium in order to store and share relevant documents at management, administrative and technical level, such as meeting agendas, draft and final versions of deliverables or dissemination activities. Nevertheless, A2C is aware that this type of cloud storages is not necessarily permanent or secure. For this reason, data collected from the different tasks that include high-risk information – such as files containing personal or sensitive information or that have a very high intellectual property or commercial value – will not be stored on them.

¹⁷ UK Data Service. *Data security*. Available at: <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/store/security>

7 Ethical aspects

A2C will be compliant with ethical guidelines as well as with the EU regulations regarding the protection of personal data. Thus, in order to adapt those guidelines and materialise in accordance with A2C objectives and characteristics, several deliverables have been or will be released facilitating that the whole consortium are aware and compliant with them. These deliverables are the following:

- D9.2 – Ethics Handbook
- D10.2 – POPD – Requirement No. 2.

Specifically, D.9.2 presents the ethical guidelines and regulations of the project. The purpose of this document is to ensure that relevant legal and ethical issues are considered. All partners are responsible for ensuring that research is conducted in compliance with the guidelines described in D.9.2, which establishes a set of fundamental principles to ensure Good Scientific Practice, the integrity of research involving human participants, and general principles of data privacy, confidentiality and security, including also a sample confidentiality agreement and consent form that will be the basis for the participation of the users to all the research activities carried-out in the framework of the Agro2Circular project

